

Induction of *A. tumefaciens virE* gene by various parts of rice plants of different ages.

Age of rice plant (d)	Part of rice plant preincubated for 72 h	Mean Miller units ± SE
4	Coleoptile	203 ± 4
	Scutellum	2919 ± 284
8	Leaf blade	501 ± 47
	Leaf base	378 ± 42
	Root	362 ± 39
14	Leaf blade	353 ± 17
	Leaf base	531 ± 22
20	Leaf blade	528 ± 75
	Leaf base	455 ± 15
Control values:	MS medium	- 175 ± 8
	MS medium + 60 µM AS	-5129 ± 90
	MS medium + tobacco leaf segments	-6840 ± 235

Scutellum-derived calli induced *vir E* expression to 1,745 Miller units, whereas scutella excised from 5-d-old seedlings and grown on 2,4-D-containing medium

induced *virE* only to about 646 Miller units. The scutellum-derived calli that induced *vir* genes more efficiently exhibited a higher level of susceptibility to *Agrobacterium* mediated transformation.

However, scutella excised from 4-d-old seedlings and grown on hormone-free medium induced *vir* gene expression to a level (2,547 Miller units) higher than that achieved with scutellum-derived calli. The results suggest that these scutella may be more susceptible to *Agrobacterium* than the scutellum-derived calli. We also found that rice scutellum promotes generation of the T-DNA transfer intermediates, T-strands, in *Agrobacterium*.

Cited references

Hiei Y, Ohta S, Komari T, Kumashiro T. 1994. Efficient transformation of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) mediated by *Agrobacterium* and sequence analysis of the boundaries of the T-DNA. *Plant J.* 6:271-282. ■

each other. A 0.52-kb *EcoRI/XhoI* fragment of a cDNA clone (RTS1) was used as a probe for screening the IR54 genomic library. A positive genomic clone (RTS2) was isolated and sequenced. Northern blot analysis (Fig. 1) and in situ hybridization (Fig. 2) showed that the gene was predominantly expressed in the anther's tapetum during vigorous meiosis and disappeared before anthesis. Sequence comparison between the cDNA clone

1. Northern blot of total RNA isolated from leaves, seeds, and panicles at various development stages and probed with putative anther-specific cDNA. Lanes with RNA are (A) leaf, (B) panicle, 4 d before C, (C) panicle when auricles of first and second leaves are at same level, (D) panicle, 4 d after C, (E) panicle, 8 d after C, (F) panicle, 12 d after C, and (G) seed.

Isolation of a tapetum-specific gene and promoter from rice

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Potential vulnerability of cytoplasmic male sterility (CMS)-derived hybrids calls for developing an alternative method of controlling male fertility/sterility for rice breeding and hybrid development. A tapetal-specific promoter-driving barnase induced sterility in tobacco and oil seed rape plants (Mariani et al 1992). Fertility was restored with the same promoter-driving barstar. Although tapetum-specific cDNA clones have recently been isolated from rice (Tsuchiya et al 1992) no regulating sequences have been reported. Developing a system by which male fertility in rice can be controlled requires a promoter that can regulate gene expression, specifically in the male organ, during anther development.

We cloned a rice anther (tapetum)-specific cDNA and corresponding genomic

DNA from rice cultivar IR54. A panicle cDNA library was constructed and differentially screened for panicle and anther specificity. We selected two cDNA clones that could be cross-hybridized with

2. In situ hybridization of transverse sections through rice spikelet, including anthers with denatured cDNA (RTS1) probe. Spikelets were sampled when auricle of first leaf was 2.5 cm above the auricle of the second leaf. (A) and (B) anthers and glumes; (C) lower magnification of A; (D) and (E) RNase-treated anthers before hybridization; and (F) leaf sheath, a = anther; t = tapetum; lo = locule; g = glume; ep = epidermis; and en = endothecium.

(RTS1) and the corresponding genomic clone (RTS2) and a primer extension assay showed that this gene has no introns and a continuous coding region of 285 base pairs yielding a putative polypeptide of 94 amino acids. The coding region of the gene has a 75.8% GC content (216/285). The nucleotide and deduced amino acid sequences, when compared with those in data banks, did not show any significant homology to known sequences. However, GAATTTGTTA, a sequence in the promoter region, differs only by one or two

nucleotides from one of the conserved sequence motifs in the promoter region of two pollen-specific genes of tomato (Twell et al 1991).

The promoter function and regulation of RTS2 for tapetum specificity may be limited to rice. Experiments to obtain rice plants transformed with *gus* A gene-containing constructs under the control of this tapetum-specific promoter are in progress. These studies will allow us to determine the DNA sequences responsible for controlling tapetum-specific expression.

Cited references

- Mariani C, Gossele V, De Beukeleert M, De Block M, Goldberg RB, De Greef M, Leeman J. 1992. Achimaeric ribonuclease-inhibitor gene restores fertility to male sterile plants. *Nature* 357:348-387.
- Twell D, Yamaguchi J, Wing RA, Ushiba J, McCormic S. 1991. Promoter analysis of genes that are coordinately expressed during pollen development reveals pollen-specific enhanced sequences and shared regulatory elements. *Gene Dev.* 5:496-507.
- Tsuchiya T, Toriyama K, Nasrallah ME, Ejiri S-I. 1992. Isolation of genes abundantly expressed in rice anther at the microscope stage. *Plant Mol. Biol.* 20:1189-1993. ■

Production and characterization of *Oryza sativa* L./*O. minuta* Presl. hybrids and backcross progenies

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We attempted to produce hybrid and backcross progenies between rice and wild species to enable the transfer of some important traits from *O. minuta* into locally cultivated rice.

Rice varieties Mahsuri, Setanjung, MR84, and MR103 were crossed with one accession of *O. minuta* (IRRI Acc. 101141), which also served as the male parent. The original F₁ hybrids and two colchicine-treated F₁s were then backcrossed to the respective *O. sativa* varieties as the recurrent parent to produce backcross 1 (BC₁). Successive backcrosses to the recurrent parents were made to produce BC₂ progenies.

Seeds of the F₁, BC₁, and BC₂ with poorly developed endosperm began to degenerate 2 wk after pollination. To ensure survival of the hybrids and BC progenies, the 14-d-old embryos were rescued on 1/4 MS medium following the procedure of Jena and Khush (1984).

Morphological characteristics, pollen fertility, somatic chromosome number, and meiotic chromosome pairing of the F₁ hybrids and BC progenies were observed.

The hybrids and BC progenies were also subjected to starch gel electrophoresis and stained for shikimate dehydrogenase (SDH), phosphogluconate dehydrogenase (PGD), and glutamate oxaloacetate transaminase (GOT) activities using the procedure described by Glaszmann et al (1988).

Seed set in *O. sativa/O. minuta* crosses ranged from 9.5 to 25.1%, depending on the rice variety used (see table). By rescuing 10- to 14-d-old embryos, 414 F₁ hybrids were successfully raised to maturity. The hybrids closely resembled their wild parent, although some of their morphological characteristics were intermediate. The male sterile F₁ plants were vigorous and tillered profusely. All had the expected chromosome number (2n=3x=36) and showed irregular meiotic chromosome pairing, with mostly univalents. Mean chromosome configuration was 29.31 (16-

36) Is + 3.32 (0-10)IIs + 0.02 (0-1)IIIs + 0.002(0-1)IVs.

Seed set in the original F₁ backcrossed with *O. sativa* parents was extremely low (0.03%); however, seed set was slightly higher (0.88%) when backcrosses were done on the colchicine-treated plants (see table). The 17 BC₁ plants obtained after embryo rescue appeared more like the F₁ and were male sterile. These plants, for which chromosome numbers varied from 44 to 48, exhibited irregular meiosis with mostly univalents.

Seed set in BC₂ was about 2.4% (see table). Of the 47 embryos cultured, 18 BC₂ plants grew to maturity and had different morphological characteristics, pollen fertility, and somatic chromosome number. Of these, one plant closely resembled the *O. sativa* parent and had 24 chromosomes. The partially fertile plant had about 58.8% pollen stainability and 12.47% spikelet fertility and showed 12 bivalents in 60% of the cells and 9-11 bivalents in the other 40% of the cells. The results showed the recovery of *O. sativa* phenotype in the

Production of *Oryza sativa/O. minuta* F₁ hybrids and backcross progenies.

Cross combination ^a	Spikelets pollinated (no.)	Seed set (%)	Embryos cultured (no.)	Plants obtained (no.)	Chromosome number (2n)
Mahsuri/ <i>O. minuta</i> (F ₁)	1,742	15.1	132	108	36
Setanjung/ <i>O. minuta</i> (F ₁)	1,729	25.1	138	123	36
MR84/ <i>O. minuta</i> (F ₁)	2,465	12.5	110	89	36
MR103/ <i>O. minuta</i> (F ₁)	2,346	9.5	112	94	36
(<i>O. sativa/O. minuta</i>) × <i>O. sativa</i> (BC ₁)	37,080	0.03	10	1	45
(CT F ₁)/ <i>O. sativa</i> (BC ₁)	3,733	0.88	33	16	44-48
(BC ₁ from CT F ₁) × <i>O. sativa</i> (BC ₂)	4,452	2.47	110	32 (18) ^a	24-37

^a CT F₁ = colchicine-treated F₁ (*O. sativa/O. minuta*). Figure in parentheses shows number of plants with normal growth.